

LEADERSHIP QUALITIES AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MADURAI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Leadership is the ability to persuade others to seek defined objectives enthusiastically. It is the human factor, which binds a group together and motivates it towards goals. Thus, leadership is the process of influencing the activities of an individual or group for goal achievement in a given situation. Leadership quality process comprises three factors – leader the follower and other variables that affect leadership process. In brief, it is the ability to influence an individual / others toward the achievement of specific goals. The source of this influence may be either formal as in an organization or informal as in politics. It is the leader who usually provides the direction toward good attainment. Leadership qualities exist in both formal and informal groups. A formal leader is one who possesses organizational authority to direct and control the activities of his subordinates. He can issue orders and instructions to his subordinates by virtue of his formal authority in the organization. Formal leaders are those appointed or elected but emerge in informal groups. They do not possess formal authority but they influence the members of the group because followers believe that the leader can provide them satisfaction. Formal leadership is institutional while informal leadership is personal.

Key Words: Leadership Qualities and Higher Secondary School Students

Need for the Study:

Leadership Qualities have played a vital role in the affairs of human beings since earliest recorded history. Historians have emphasized heroes in battle and the importance of their deeds for the future course of history. In modern society, organizational functions are being carried out by individuals characterized differently in different situations and time, and their contributions are praised. Some individuals contribute more of their energies or skills than others and they vary in their extent to which they exert influence over each other: Leaders guide not only individuals but also organization and determine goals of organizations. In a developing society leader is required to motivate others, seek their cooperation, ensure commitment, take important decisions etc. effective leader can ensure positive growth and development in society. Otherwise, the society will meet with disastrous effects. There are varied ways on the need for leadership qualities for the higher secondary school students. So the present study intends to measure to leadership quality among the higher secondary school students which is entitled the present study, "Leadership Quality among Higher Secondary School Students". Hence, he is interested in carrying out this research.

Terms and Definitions:

Leadership Qualities – refer to the ability of an individual to higher secondary school students to influence, motivate and enable himself and others to contribute effectively in daily works of school life and society.

Higher Secondary School Students – refer to those who are studying XI and XII standard students.

Madurai District - refers to one of the southern districts of Tamil Nadu state.

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variables:

- Leadership Qualities

Independent Variables:

- Gender : Male/Female
- Community : ST&SC/Others
- Religion : Hindu/Others
- Residence : Rural / Urban

Objectives of the Study:

The specific objectives of the study are listed below:

- To measure the leadership qualities among higher secondary school students in Madurai district.
- To find out whether there is significant differences in leadership qualities among higher secondary school students in terms of select independent variables viz. gender, community, religion, residence,

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following hypotheses have been formulated for verification in this study.

- Leadership qualities among the higher secondary school students are above average.
- Gender exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.

- Community exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.
- Religion exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.
- Residence exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.

Methodology:

Sample:

A random sample of 324 secondary school teachers in Madurai district with due representation to the variables viz. gender, community, religion, residence.

Tools Used:

The tools used for data collection were as follows:

- General Information sheet structured by the investigator.
- Leadership Qualities Scale by Jeevaraj, J (2014).

Statistical Treatment:

- Significance of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation.
- 't'- test for finding out the significance of difference between the means of large sub-groups of independent samples.

Related Studies:

The Leadership Practices of Middle and High School Principals by Leech, Donald W.; Fulton, C. Ray (2002) reports a descriptive study of principals in a large urban school district. They examine the differences in middle school and high-school teachers' perceptions of the leadership practices of educational leaders. The sample consists of 242 participants from 12 middle schools and 404 participants from 14 high 73 schools. Each participant was administered Kouzes and Posner's Leadership Practices Inventory, which identified the teachers' perceptions of their principals' leadership practices in each of five dimensions: (1) challenging the process; (2) inspiring a shared vision; (3) enabling others to act; (4) modeling the way; and (5) encouraging the heart. No significant differences were identified between the means of the responses of middle school and high-school teachers for any of the five practices: Middle school and high-school teachers reported similar perceptions of their principals' leadership practices. Additional analysis indicates that both middle school and high-school principals most often exhibited the practices of "enabling others to act" and "modeling the way" and least often demonstrated the behavior of "encouraging the heart."

A Study of Leadership Behaviors of Elementary Principals Compared with School Climate was conducted by Mendel, Christine M.; Watson, Robert L.; Macgregor, Cynthia J. (1999) In this study, leadership was examined as a factor in the creation of good schools. Eight principals of high-performing schools in New York City were interviewed. Four common features among the principals interviewed include controlling staff hiring and development practices, experience, creating and maintaining a coherent educational mission throughout all grades, and having high expectations for student autonomy is often neglected in the literature. The authors recommend that large bureaucratic school systems grant principals greater autonomy, particularly as principals prove capable of generating success. Accountability will be preserved. Greater autonomy is likely to encourage more effective leaders to emerge and to stay in New York City and other urban public schools.

Transformational Leadership: Principals, Leadership Teams, and School Culture by Lucas, Stephen Earl; Valentine, Jerry Wayne; (2002) was undertaken to develop an understanding of the relationships among principal transformational leadership, school leadership-team transformational leadership, and school culture. Twelve middle schools composed the sample population. Three surveys were used, each one focusing on collecting data related to principal leadership, team leadership, and school culture. Data were analyzed using correlation and regression statistics. Results show that the principal seems to be the primary source of identifying and articulating a vision and providing an appropriate model. Leadership teams seem to be the primary source of providing intellectual stimulation and holding high expectations. There is a mix of principal and leadership-team influence as sources of fostering commitment to group goals and providing individualized support. School culture factors reveal that the leadership team, rather than the principal, seems to exert the greatest influence upon collaborative leadership and learning partnership. The principal, rather than leadership teams, seems to exert the greatest influence upon teacher collaboration and unity of purpose. These and other findings are supportive of the current movement in education toward collaborative forms of school leadership. This study serves as a start for further exploration of principals, leadership teams, transformational leadership, and school culture.

Hypotheses Verification:

Hypothesis 1: Leadership qualities among the higher secondary school students' is above average.

The average score of the Leadership qualities among the higher secondary school students is found to be 58.67, while the theoretical average is 56. This shows that the Leadership quality among the higher secondary school students' is above the average level. It means that higher secondary school students are found aware of leadership qualities moderately. Hence the hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: Gender exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.

The statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of leadership qualities among higher secondary school students in terms of the gender are presented in Table 1.

Variable	Sub-category	N	Mean	Standard deviation	' t' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	201	57.16	11.23	3.024	Significant
	Female	123	56.34	10.68		

The calculated 't' value 3.024 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between male and female secondary school students in possession of leadership qualities. It can be inferred from the above finding that male students of secondary schools possess more leadership qualities than their counterparts. Hence the hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Community exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.

The statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of leadership qualities among higher secondary school students in terms of the Community are presented in Table 2.

Variable	Sub-category	N	Mean	Standard deviation	' t' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Community	ST&SC	145	57.98	11.05	1.192	Not Significant
	Others	179	55.14	10.21		

The calculated 't' value 1.192 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between SC&ST and others secondary school students in possession of leadership qualities. It can be inferred from the Community does not influence on leadership qualities among secondary school students. Hence the hypothesis 3 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4: Religion exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.

The statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of leadership qualities among higher secondary school students in terms of the Religion are presented in Table 3.

Variable	Sub-category	N	Mean	Standard deviation	' t' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Religion	Hindu	217	57.21	11.85	1.125	Not Significant
	Others	107	54.58	10.12		

The calculated 't' value 1.125 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between Hindu and others secondary school students in possession of leadership qualities. It can be inferred from the Religion does not influence on leadership qualities among secondary school students. Hence the hypothesis 4 is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: Residence exerts a significant influence on leadership qualities among higher secondary school students.

The statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of leadership qualities among higher secondary school students in terms of the Residence are presented in Table 4.

Variable	Sub-category	N	Mean	Standard deviation	' t' value	Significance at 0.05 level
Residence	Rural	136	56.17	11.76	-2.141	Significant
	Urban	188	57.54	10.42		

The calculated 't' value -2.141 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between rural and urban residency secondary school students in possession of leadership qualities. It can be inferred from the urban residency students possess more leadership qualities than rural residency students. Hence the hypothesis 5 is accepted.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions arrived at from the study are listed below:

- Leadership qualities among higher secondary school students are found high.
- Leadership qualities among higher secondary school students is found dependent upon-
 - Gender
 - Residence
- Leadership qualities among higher secondary school students is found independent upon-
 - Community
 - Religion

Educational Implications:

The present investigation was designed to measure the leadership qualities of secondary school teachers in Madurai district. For this purpose a stratified random sample of 324 higher secondary school students was constituted with due representation to the select population (independent) variables.

The study has revealed that the gender plays an important role on either increasing or decreasing the leadership qualities connected with the area of education. As usual the male students have slightly upper hand in leadership role in education. So, the concerned authorities should undertake appropriate programmes for enhancing the level of leadership qualities among female students. Besides the level of leadership qualities is just above the average among both the male and female students. It is very useful to enhance the level of leadership qualities among higher secondary school students to the maximum level to raise the quality of secondary education in Madurai district. This may be true to other districts with certain reservations.

Residence also plays a vital role in leadership qualities among higher secondary school students. The out of the research shows that urban students do well in leadership qualities. Efforts should be taken for the upliftment of the leadership qualities among the rural higher secondary school students also immediately.

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